

The Effectiveness of the Discussion Method in Elementary School: A Case in Jayapura District- Indonesia

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Abstract

To use the discussion method in a lesson, the Christian Religious Education teachers must understand well the principles and basics of the discussion method. They should do understand what the essence of the discussion material is. This paper shows that it is essential to understand and master the discussion method as a teacher before using it. For this reason, a teacher is required to have skills regarding this discussion method. This paper presents the phenomena of classroom action research that applied two cycles before using the discussion method and after applying the technique in an elementary school in Jayapura, Indonesia.

1. Introduction

The teacher is the determinant of the future of the students. The teacher is also a determinant of student change (Tolnaiová, 2021; Sari & Surbakti, 2021). If the teacher only pursues, then the learning values that have been obtained in the classroom as a result of learning will not be a guarantee for student success in the future. But the values will be meaningful if they result from the teacher's best efforts and struggles and change the hearts and minds of students. Li & Wong (2021) state that the teacher must be aware that he is the determinant of the future and sustainability of the existence of a nation. Because teachers educate and prepare the next generation. Therefore, teachers must be serious and seriously trained and creative in carrying out their roles and duties properly in the teaching and learning process at school and outside of school (Donoghue et al., 2021).

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Teachers must dare to instil in students a feeling of self-worth and self-confidence. With their abilities, students can learn and have the ability to dream big and think positively (Benchetrit, R., & Katz, 2019). For example, an inspirational world education figure named Ron Clark, founder of Ron Clark Academy in Atlanta, Georgia, said. If you (teachers) bring positive energy into an area, then negative energy will have no choice but to leave (Cf. Smiley et al., 2022).

Many learning methods can be learned by teachers and adapted to the learning objectives to be achieved in a teaching and learning process. To use the discussion method in a lesson, the Christian Religious Education (CRE) teacher must understand the principles and basics of the discussion method (Cf. Ying, 2020). With the correct understanding of the application of the discussion method in the teaching and learning process, CRE teachers will be able to lead, guide, organize, organize and direct the teaching and learning process that they carry out according to existing procedures. If the teacher does not understand the basis of the discussion method, then tries to use it in teaching and learning activities, the discussion will widen and even impact students because they do not understand the essence of the discussion material. This shows that it is very important to understand and master the discussion method as a teacher before using it. For this reason, a teacher is required to have the skills or skills regarding this discussion method.

Even learning using the discussion method, the ability of CRE teachers is still very lacking. This can be seen from the CRE teacher not being able to create conducive conditions for all students to learn using the discussion method. Most students are not proactive, students do not talk much or are silent, students do not dare to express their thoughts and opinions regarding the subject being discussed. According to the researcher, there must be students who have academic abilities above their friends. In addition, there must be students who talk a lot but have low abilities.

On the other hand, it can also be seen that the quality of their CRE learning is very low. This can cause the CRE lessons to be less meaningful for students, causing students' learning activities to be below, and learning tends to be passive. In fact, in the 2013 Curriculum (in Indonesia), the teaching approach used in learning activities creates activeness in student learning. Suppose it is associated with using the discussion method as a learning model. In that case, students' activeness should be seen because the basic thing from the 2013 curriculum learning model required in the learning process is student activity. Student activities are not only listening and taking notes but are more focused on activities or student participation in the learning process. The use of the discussion method is more likely to result in teaching and learning activities that may be scary for students. Conditions like this are very unfavourable for teachers and students. Teachers get failures in delivering scientific messages, and students are harmed. To improve students' mastery of CRE concepts and principles, the presentation of CRE teaching materials in class V of YPK Ifar Babrongko elementary school using the discussion method must be appropriate if you want to see student activity in the teaching and learning process.

Learning CRE using the discussion method for the fifth-grade students of SD YPK Ifar Babrongko found the following problems: 1) The activity of students in making and conveying their ideas was still very low; 2) Lack of courage to express an opinion; 3) Another problem that is often found at this time is the lack of students' ability to master the subject matter; (4) The application of discussion methods that are not following the teaching objectives will be an obstacle in achieving the goals that have been formulated; (5) Quite a lot of CRE lesson materials are wasted just because the method is used according to the teacher's wishes and ignores student needs, facilities, and situations class; (6) CRE teachers have used the discussion method while the aim of teaching is so that students can be active in it, but it is unfortunate because teaching and learning activities are not as expected because they are not conducive. CRE teachers applying the discussion method is expected to increase student activity in CRE learning at SD YPK Babrongko.

The application of the discussion method should be able to support the achievement of teaching goals, not goals that must adapt to the method (Nhan, 2018). This is an important note for CRE teachers to look for know if the class discussion does not go according to the principles of the method or conduct a self-evaluation to improve the quality of teaching. However, in reality, based on the author's observations, the teaching and learning process for CRE subjects in Ifar Babrongko's fifth grade elementary school is only oriented to the demands of the curriculum that have been outlined in the textbook. Learning in the classroom is still dominated by lectures from the teacher. Students' activities can be said to only listen to the teacher's explanation and record what the teacher is saying.

The effectiveness of the application of the discussion method can occur if there is a match between the method and all teaching components that have been programmed in the lesson unit as written preparation. From the description above, it is necessary to understand and realize that students are the subject of education. This means that most of the success of education depends on the factors of the educational method used. The teaching and learning process will be successful if the method is attractive to students. The knowledge of the discussion method that the CRE teacher has learned can be used to teach his students. Thus, CRE teachers can transfer knowledge appropriately because they use the method correctly.

Therefore, Christian Religious Education (CRE) teachers are required to have good skills and mastery in applying discussion methods to create and increase student activity in learning. In addition, CRE teachers must pay attention to and properly analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the discussion method to develop a correct and good lesson plan.

2. Materials and Method

This research is classroom action research or also known as CAR (Classroom Action Research), namely research conducted by teachers in their classrooms, to correct problems in the classroom (Cf. Meesuk et al., 2020). The subjects in this study were fifth-grade students of SD (Elementary School) YPK Ifar Babrongko, Waibu District, Jayapura Regency- Indonesia. The total number of students in the class is 29 people, which are divided into 12 boys and 17 girls at SD YPK Ifar Babrongko Academic year 2021/2022.

3. Results and Discussion

Cycle I Implementasi Implementation Results

Students have not been able to answer correctly because they have not found their interest in learning and are not concentrating, so they do not appear enthusiastic to answer questions in the discussions at that time. The results of the implementation of the first cycle provide an illustration that what the researcher wants to achieve is still an evaluation material for carrying out an action plan in the second cycle.

Cycle II Implementation Results

From the previous activity, it can be seen that the data on the results of the initial test on October 1, 2021, shows that 17 students did not complete and 19% of the learning outcomes were incomplete, while on the other hand, students who answered the questions well so that they developed as expected or their learning outcomes were completed as much as four people so that it reaches a presentation of 81%. After presenting the material in the first cycle, there was an increase in the

absorption of the subject matter with the achievement of learning completeness as many as nine people so that it obtained a percentage of 57% of students or in other words, it could be said that there was an increase of 24% after the initial test. Now in cycle II, there is an increase again to 18 students who can answer well or in other words, 86% of students can absorb lessons well and have reached the category of developing as expected and even developing very well or completely, while students who are not able to work on questions only 14% or three students from 21 fifth grade students of SD YPK Ifar Babrongko.

From the description of the data on the acquisition of self-regulated learning scores, the results obtained from 79.6% of students, most of them had moderate self-regulated learning. Meanwhile, 20.4% of students with high SRL and low SRL did not get the lowest score. This shows that students who have moderate SRL cannot manage to learn well. At the same time, the acquisition of learning achievement scores obtained by the students' learning outcomes of State Junior High Schools in Sentani City showed that most of the 42.6% students had moderate learning achievements. While 41.3% of students have high learning outcomes, and students have low learning achievements are 16.1%.

In addition, the regression analysis results show a significant correlation between self-regulated learning and learning achievement of 0.873. These findings indicate that self-regulated learning greatly influences the learning achievement of State Junior High School students in Sentani City.

The SRL instrument tested for validity, reliability and factor analysis can be developed for students of SMP Negeri Sentani, Jayapura Regency so that students can improve their learning achievement.

Discussion

a. Cycle I

The students' test results in the first cycle were; only nine students achieved completeness with a percentage of 43%, while those who had not achieved completeness were 12 students with a percentage of 57%. For this reason, it is hoped that after the teaching and learning process in cycle II, these 12 students can achieve more mastery results.

b. Cycle II

The test results of students in cycle II achieved good results as the highest achievement (B) there were 18 students with a percentage of 86%, it was stated that they had achieved learning mastery. And students who are very less (SK) as many as three students with a percentage of 14% do not achieve complete learning. Students who do not achieve complete learning are also given assignments, additional homework and enrichment or remediation.

4. Conclusion

Based on this research, the researcher can convey some suggestions as follows. First, in carrying out the learning process in elementary schools, a teacher should be able to find suitable methods for students and, more specifically, methods that are better able to meet all students' needs in understanding learning (Cf. Fan et al., 2018).

Second, in carrying out the discussion method, the teacher should do it completely and seriously so that the process of applying the discussion method can encourage students to continue to learn and shape students' personalities to continue to be better (Cf. Howe et al., 2019). Third, future

research needs to be conducted to improve student learning outcomes in applying the discussion method.

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